

COMMON WADDEN SEA SECRETARIAT

GREY SEAL NUMBERS IN THE WADDEN SEA AND HELGOLAND IN 2025-2026

INTRODUCTION

Since the 1980s, the Atlantic grey seal has been re-colonising the Wadden Sea and Helgoland and has established breeding sites in the area (Brasseur *et al.*, 2015; Abt and Engler 2009). The grey seal is protected under the European Habitats Directive and included in the most recent [Seal Management Plan of the Wadden Sea \(SMP 2023-2032\)](#). To comply with the reporting obligations from these legal instruments, trilaterally coordinated surveys have been conducted since 2008 to count grey seals on sandbanks in the Wadden Sea across Denmark, Germany, and the Netherlands, as well as at Helgoland. Surveys are carried out during both the pupping (November to January), and moulting seasons (March and April). In the pupping season, adult females give birth and suckle their white-coated pups, preferably on high sandbanks that do not flood during high tide. In favourable conditions, the newborn pups will stay on the sandbank throughout the lactating period (3 weeks) and remain there as they shed their white fur, replacing it with a grey coat (duration of 1-4 weeks) (Kovacs and Lavigne, 1985), before they leave the haul-out site.

During the moulting season, characterised by seals showing a

visible change in fur colour (Schop *et al.* 2017), large numbers of hauled-out grey seals are observed. It is assumed that moulting seals lower their energetic costs by hauling out and limiting immersion into the colder water (Paterson *et al.*, 2012). Aerial surveys are conducted in all areas, and additional land-based counts are performed at Helgoland.

Grey seals in the Wadden Sea and Helgoland are part of the wider North Sea population, with movements occurring between haul-out sites within this region (Brasseur *et al.*, 2015; 2022, Carter *et al.*, 2026). During the moulting season, individuals from other North Sea colonies (particularly from the larger populations in the United Kingdom) also use Wadden Sea haul-outs, influencing the total counts (Brasseur *et al.*, 2015). As a result, the counts presented here reflect not only the numbers predominantly occurring in the Wadden Sea Conservation Area, but also those that occur in the broader region of the North Sea.

This report presents updated grey seal count data from the Wadden Sea and Helgoland between 2008-2026. To provide the most accurate trend analysis, we use the surveys recorded within the shortest possible time window across the different survey

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regions. This approach minimises the risk of double-counting individuals that move between regions. Because some seals are at sea during surveys, the numbers should be interpreted as indices rather than an absolute population size. These indices are most informative when analysed over multiple years, as annual fluctuations can occur due to weather, disturbances, or other local and regional factors.

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PUP COUNTS

During the pupping season of 2025-2026, coordinated counts across the Wadden Sea and Helgoland resulted in a total count of 3,385 grey seal pups (right-hand figure). This is a 10.9% increase compared to the 2024-2025 season (Schop *et al.*, 2025). During the last five years the number of counted pups increased by 12.2% on average.

Most of the pups were counted in the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea, comprising 51.1% of the total pup count this year, followed by Helgoland (31.8%) and Lower Saxony (17.0%). Within the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea, the count of 1,731 pups represented a 5.5% increase compared to the previous pupping season. The number of pups at Helgoland increased by 11.0% to 1,077. In Lower Saxony, there was a 22.3% increase compared to the last season, resulting in 575 pups. Within the time window when most pups were counted in the whole Wadden Sea area, one pup was recorded in both Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark.

Number of grey seal pups counted during pupping season in the Wadden Sea and Helgoland between 2007-2008 and 2025-2026
Colours indicate results of the regional counts.

MOULT COUNTS

Number of grey seals counted in the Wadden Sea regions and Helgoland during the moult in March-April between 2008 and 2026

Colours indicate results of the regional counts.

● Denmark ● Schleswig-Holstein ● Helgoland ● Lower Saxony and Hamburg ● Netherlands ● Total

In 2026, a total of 12,497 grey seals were counted during the moulting season in the Wadden Sea; a 3.6% increase compared to 2025 (Schop *et al.* 2025; left-hand figure). In the entire Wadden Sea area and Helgoland, an annual growth of 6.8% was detected over the last five years.

Approximately 71.8% of the grey seals counted during the moult were observed in the Dutch part of the Wadden Sea (8,981 grey seals, an increase of 4.0% compared to 2025). Lower Saxony contributed 9.8% to the total count with 1,222 grey seals, and 7.9% (989 grey seals) were recorded at Helgoland. For Lower Saxony this constitutes a decrease in numbers of 21.9% and for Helgoland a decrease of 6.7% compared to the previous year. The number of grey seals counted in the Wadden Sea area of Schleswig-Holstein almost doubled from 499 animals in 2025, to 957 seals in 2026. In the Danish Wadden Sea, 348 grey seals were counted this year, 45 more than in 2025. Grey seals are highly mobile. Numbers of counted grey seals can fluctuate from day to day, depending on how many seals are at sea or hauled out, which is why also the average growth over five years is given instead of only annually.

DISCUSSION

Although trilateral surveys aim to produce a complete count for the entire Wadden Sea, the timing of the pupping peak seems to differ between the regions. In the eastern Wadden Sea (Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark) pups are observed later in the season (i.e. in late December and January). This pattern resembles observations from newly established colonies in the United Kingdom, where less experienced females tend to give birth later in the season (Bull *et al.*, 2021), and observations in the Dutch Wadden Sea where the peak in pup numbers moved from January to the beginning of December (Brasseur *et al.*, 2015). This suggests that the grey seal breeding population in the Wadden Sea is still developing in some parts and may continue to grow if the species increasingly occupies the eastern Wadden Sea.

The increase in grey seal numbers during the moulting season in the eastern Wadden Sea is remarkable, particularly given the relatively low number of pups recorded in this region. A similar, though even more pronounced, pattern is observed in the Dutch Delta region (outside the Wadden Sea): 4,267 grey seals were counted during the moulting season 2025, compared with only 47 pups recorded during the

breeding period 2024 (Hoekstein *et al.*, 2026). Telemetry studies have shown that individual harbour seals migrate towards known breeding sites just before the breeding season (Brasseur *et al.*, 2017). Grey seals also show fidelity for their breeding sites, and grey seals observed in the Dutch Wadden Sea, migrate to the United Kingdom during the breeding season (Brasseur *et al.*, 2015; 2017). Seals observed in the eastern Wadden Sea (Schleswig-Holstein and Denmark) and the Dutch Delta region, might breed on breeding sites in the Wadden Sea or Helgoland. Galatius *et al.* (2024) reported higher numbers of Atlantic grey seals in Danish Kattegat during the moulting period compared to the Baltic subspecies, which indicates a mix of the two subspecies in that region. If the breeding population in the eastern Wadden Sea continues to grow, increased exchange between Atlantic and Baltic grey seals is likely, potentially influencing both population structure and seasonal distribution patterns. In addition, the Dutch Delta area contributed substantially to the total number of grey seals on the continental side of the North Sea. We should therefore consider including the surveys of these adjacent areas in our evaluation (both Baltic and Dutch Delta), as they could affect numbers in the Wadden Sea.

CONCLUSION

The counts of both grey seal pups and moulting grey seals in the Wadden Sea and Helgoland were higher in 2025-2026 compared to the 2024-2025 season. A total of 3,385 seal pups and 12,497 moulting seals were counted. The pup count has shown an average annual growth rate of 12.2% over the past five years, while the number of grey seals counted during the moult has increased at an annual rate of 6.8% during the same period.

To improve the timing of the surveys, a good understanding is needed of

the timing when most grey seals are on land for breeding and moulting. For management and advice, it is recommended to investigate the movements of grey seals breeding in the Wadden Sea and neighbouring regions to enhance understanding of exchange with other areas and potential pressures. Having a greater knowledge of the wider population, will help understand observations in the Wadden Sea area, hence it is advisable to include the neighbouring regions in the survey coordination and annual trilateral report.

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